

Directionality and Public Sector Capabilities for the Twin Transition in Local Government

Veronika Bylicki

Research Assistant,
UCL Institute for Innovation and Public Purpose

Rainer Kattel

Deputy Director and Professor of Innovation and Public Governance,
UCL Institute for Innovation and Public Purpose

Anna Kurth

Research Assistant,
UCL Institute for Innovation and Public Purpose

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Directionality and public sector capabilities for the twin transition in local governments¹

Veronika Bylicki, Rainer Kattel, and Anna Kurth

Abstract

This paper explores the implementation of the twin transition in the Spanish city of Barcelona and the London borough of Camden. We examine how these two urban areas are conceptualising and governing the twin transition. We focus on the types of directionality that are embedded in the twin transition and how they relate to the distinct capabilities required for government to implement them. We find that the different directionalities underlying the green, digital and twin transitions require different capabilities for their implementation. This is because the green transition is driven by normative, political goals, while the digital transition is driven by economic and efficiency goals, and the twin transition seems to be predominantly a rhetorical construct not used in city practice. As a result, we show how local governments have developed separate strategies and capabilities to advance digital and green transitions, without any effective focus on twin transition. Our findings have implications for policymakers at all levels of government. First, policymakers need to be aware of the different directionalities underlying the green and digital transitions. Second, in order to advance the twin transition, policymakers need to develop a unique set of capabilities that is tailored to the specific challenges of the twin transition.

Keywords: Twin transition; Directionality; Public Sector Capabilities; Cities

Reference

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1. Introduction

There is a growing focus among researchers and practitioners in the urban policy space on transformative change and city government capacities to drive such change (e.g., Wolfram, 2016; Bhatia et al, 2024; Hölscher et al, 2019; Hölscher, 2020). While most of the discussion and practice has focused on sustainability issues, there is growing interest in a broader issue of directionality of transformative change, partially driven by a new generation of mission-oriented policies and other market-shaping policies (e.g., green industrial strategy) (Grillitsch, Coenen and Morgan, 2023; Mazzucato, 2021; Stirling, 2024). The issue of directionality has become particularly relevant in the European context, partially due to the adoption of a new EU-wide Mission for 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030, but perhaps more importantly because of its so-called twin transition: a combination of green and digital transformation. The twin transition policy agenda does not interrogate whether the directionality implicit in both green and digital transformations is of a similar or different nature. Moreover, the policy agenda does not ask whether these two transitions rely on similar public sector capabilities to implement them. These questions – the nature of directionality in the twin transition and the capabilities required – form the core of this paper.

We investigate these questions through a comparative case study of two leading European local governments, the city of Barcelona and one of London's boroughs, Camden. The case selection is driven by the argument that by looking at two quite different contexts in what could in many ways be regarded as best-of-class local governments in green and digital transitions, we can learn how city governments are conceptualising and practicing twin transition as directionalities, and how they are deploying and developing capabilities for such transitions.

The paper is structured as follows: first, in the theory section, we delve into the nature of directionality, and how digital and green transitions map on to our theoretical understanding; we finish this section by briefly describing the linkages and gaps between directionality and public sector capacity research. The second section describes our methodological approach and justification for case selection. This is followed by case descriptions, and we finish by bringing the discussion back to our main theoretical questions about the nature of directionality and public sector capacities in twin transition.

2. Operationalising directionality in the context of the green and digital transition

Twin Transition

The complex relationship between digitalisation and sustainability transitions has gained prominence in socio-technical transitions research and practice (Andersen et al, 2021; Mäkitie et al, 2023; Sareen and Haarstad, 2021; Wurm and Wittmann, 2023; Fouquet and Hippe, 2022). The twin transition describes the interplay between the digital and green transitions in society, emphasising how digitalisation affects sustainability efforts and how these processes are interconnected (Dæhlen, 2023, p. 12). While both transitions promise to reshape societies and economies, their characteristics diverge: the green transition necessitates immediate political and societal action to achieve climate neutrality, whereas the digital transition is influenced by private-sector innovation and thus is biased towards economic efficiency goals (Muench et al, 2022). This requires the public sector to ensure alignment with equitable and sustainable goals (Muench et al, 2022). The two transitions have different underlying evolutionary logics: The digital transition emerged through techno-economic evolution and is driven endogenously by capitalism. The green transition is largely driven by political demand to stay within planetary boundaries (Lema and Perez, 2023). To unlock the potential of the twin transition and to prevent negative effects, the EU strives to connect the green and digital transitions through 'proactive and integrated management' (Muench et al, 2022). This rationale for linking the transitions is mainly political (Wurm and Wittman, 2023): With its twin transition agenda, the EU connects its political priorities of digitalisation and sustainability, and leverages them jointly as an opportunity for economic growth (Muench et al, 2022). Consequently, the twin transition serves as both a mechanism for advancing sustainability and a tool for driving the EU's economic objectives.

Digital tools can both advance and hinder the green transition at the instrumental and institutional level (Mäkitie et al, 2023; Meijer, 2024; Meijer and Ruijter, 2023). Producing and consuming digital technologies has a significant material footprint (Al Kez et al, 2022). Mäkitie et al (2023) introduce a typology categorising how digital innovations contribute to sustainability transitions, distinguishing among incremental twin innovations, sustainability-supported digital innovations, digitally supported sustainable innovations and radical twin innovations. They argue that radical twin innovations possess the biggest potential for sustainability transitions, because they are linked to structural change, while incremental innovations primarily optimise existing, unsustainable systems. Similarly, Meijer (2024) critiques the current literature for insufficiently addressing the institutional dimensions of the twin transition, asserting a need to study not only direct, instrumental relations between e-governance and sustainable development, but also to 'expand to the fundamental ontological and normative foundations of dominant perspectives.' Integrating insights from research on the capacities required for green and digital transitions, Meijer and Ruijter (2023) propose that, while the transitions are distinct, they converge in the capabilities necessary to enable them. It thus is important to further explore the normative foundations and institutional dimensions of the twin transition, as well as the public sector capabilities needed to implement them.

Directionality in sustainability transformations

Public sector organisations play a critical role in shaping the direction of innovation activities (Mazzucato, 2013, 2016), articulating societal needs into actionable demand (Boon and Edler, 2018) and breaking up path dependencies (Schot and Steinmueller, 2018). Weber and Rohracher (2012) argue societal challenge-led innovation policies are necessary because of 'transformational' system failures, including a lack of directionality. In this context, Stirling (2024) identifies three interrelated but distinct meanings of directionality that are often conflated: '(a) the directing of innovation (driving processes under given ends); (b) the direction of innovation (steering pathways towards chosen ends); and (c) the directionality of innovation (grasping multiplicities of plural ends).' There is general agreement on the utility of setting ambitious, well-defined and measurable goals to guide smaller scale, technology-focused missions, as could be related to the digital transition (e.g. Diercks et al, 2019; Schot and Steinmueller, 2018; Robinson and Mazzucato, 2019). However, whether such approaches are applicable to broader societal missions, such as the green transition, remains contested. Some scholars advocate for concrete targets to help actors align their efforts (e.g. Mazzucato, 2018; Hekkert et al, 2020; Wittmann et al, 2021). Others, in line with Stirling's definition of the directionality of innovation, view transformative missions as inherently open-ended, arguing that rigid goal-setting narrows pathways and reduces adaptability (Kuhlmann and Rip, 2018; Schot and Steinmueller, 2018).

Overall, the directionality behind the twin transition remains underexplored. Given the different dynamics driving the green and digital transition, and these different meanings of directionality, we hypothesise that different directionalities apply to the green, digital and twin transitions respectively.

Public sector capabilities for transformation

In past decades, various forms of what can be called transformation research have been carried out, predominantly in urban planning, sustainability transitions and public management literature (Kattel et al 2025). And while these discussions have topicalised capacities to transform systems, the directionality question has remained implicit. Thus, for instance, the most comprehensive theoretical coding and synthesis in urban planning literature has been proposed by Wolfram (2016). Their focus is on the ability to 'disrupt and dismantle existing systems, and to simultaneously create and build up viable alternatives' within an urban context (Wolfram et al, 2019, 438). Similarly, for more than 20 years the sustainability transitions literature has analysed how socio-technical change happens, including the interaction between emerging niches and extant regimes (Geels, 2002), and policy leverage points for systems change (Kanger et al, 2020), and related capacities (Hölscher et al, 2019; also Borrás et al, 2024). Public management literatures have recently focused on operationalising the above-mentioned activities and capacities into concrete tasks (Braams et al, 2023). However, in all these core literatures, directionality is often implicitly assumed as an exogenous normative goal (e.g. political sustainability goals) or as a feature of long-term systems change (e.g. co-evolutionary patterns of technical change).

In addition, emerging discussions around the dynamic and agile capabilities of public sector organisations have focused on detailing how public organisations can develop and deploy capabilities to adapt and transform existing policies and services (e.g. Kattel, 2022; Mergel, 2022), and have not touched upon the question of directionality in relation to such capabilities.

Following Lember et al (2025), we propose to conceptualise capabilities for twin transformation on three generic levels: ‘transition governance, such as shaping overall aims, articulating values and framing problems at the transition landscape level; transition pathways, which entails organizational strategies and collaborative practices as well as the choice and design of policy; and innovation projects as transition experiments, which are the key sources of novelty’ (our emphasis).

Table 1: Synthesis of public sector capabilities for transformative policies

	Main concepts	Key capabilities
Transition governance	Governance of transformative (innovation) policies (Janssen et al, 2023)	Creating legitimacy and leadership; coordinating across multiple levels, actors and instruments; reflexivity, learning and experimenting; resolving conflicts
Organisational strategies	Roles for public sector organisations (Borrás et al, 2024) Dynamic capabilities (Kattel, 2022) Transition tasks for civil servants (Braams et al, 2022)	Destabilise, create or maintain institutions Sense-making, connecting, seizing and transforming Give direction, support governance, support the new, destabilise the unsustainable, and develop internal capabilities and structures
Innovation portfolios	Abilities to manage innovation portfolios of multiple projects across diverse policy domains (Borrás et al, 2024)	Analytical abilities (exploring, studying, investigating...) Operational abilities (exploiting, managing, executing...) Coordination abilities (collaborating, connecting, communicating...) Learning and reflectivity abilities (incorporating new understandings, adjusting...)

Across the three dimensions of capabilities, we can see that directionality plays an important if implicit role.

Combining twin transition, public sector capabilities, and directionality

The twin transition policy agenda and public sector capabilities discussions often overlook whether the directionality inherent in green and digital transformations is of a similar or divergent nature. Recent studies have begun to address this gap by examining the distinct challenges posed by the two transitions and their implications for innovation directionality (Wanzenböck et al, 2020; Wurm and Wittmann, 2023). Wanzenböck et al (2020) propose a framework to assess whether societal challenges encounter directionality failures, emphasising that differing constellations of converging or diverging perspectives on a policy issue necessitate distinct

policy responses. Building on this framework, Wurm and Wittmann (2023) find that substantial portions of the relatively nascent twin transition remain in a state of disorientation, where societal views on problems and solutions diverge. Therefore, they argue that there is a need for a bundle of twin transition strategies that address each policy issue's unique position in the problem-solution space. For policy issues where societal views on problems and solutions diverge significantly, policymakers should follow a discovery approach, centred on basic research, experiments and monitoring. For policy areas where societal views are located closer together in the problem-solution space, synergies in policymaking approaches between the green and digital transition can be leveraged. This calls for further research on how policy can meaningfully address different dynamics behind the green, digital and twin transitions, and how public sector capabilities shape and are shaped by directionality.

Based on the context described above, we expect different directionalities to pertain to the green and digital transitions. On the one hand, the green transition has a political goal (reducing emissions), which is closely connected with social issues (such as ideas around a just transition), which opens up 'irreducible plurality of possibility in a balanced way' ('directionality of innovation') (Stirling, 2024, p.14). On the other hand, the digital transition requires collaboration with private sector stakeholders and is primarily about increasing economic efficiency. This involves 'steering selected possible pathways rather than others' ('direction of innovation') (Stirling, 2024, p.14).

We can summarise the existing discussions in the following propositions: first, as directionality is under-conceptualised in twin transition, we would expect the directionality to be expressed in policy practice quite differently, without clear synthesis and convergence; second, moving from directing innovations to directionality of innovation, as proposed by Stirling, increases the demand for, and complexity of, public sector capabilities. These propositions are summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Directionality and public sector capabilities

We hypothesise that since digital and green transitions are based on two different kinds of directionalities (green transitions are driven largely by normative, political goals, whereas digital transitions are predominantly driven by economic and efficiency goals), cities develop separate strategies and capabilities to advance twin transition. Because of these different types of directionalities inherent in the green and digital transitions, we hypothesise that the twin transition, too, has a distinct underlying directionality which requires a unique set of capabilities to be achieved.

3. Methodological note

In this paper we present a comparative case study of the London Borough of Camden and Barcelona City Council. The cases can be seen as ‘outliers’ as both are relatively well-known for their leadership in urban transitions. Camden is a pioneer in participatory approaches to the green transition and held the UK’s first citizen assembly on the climate crisis in 2019. It is also the first local government in the UK to apply missions as a governance tool. Barcelona is a leader in the smart city movement, green spaces and urban planning, and sustainable urban mobility. Yet, their contextual differences are considerable, from administrative traditions to legal mandates. Under the UK’s centralised administrative tradition, local councils like Camden operate within strict statutory frameworks set by central government, such as the many Local Government Acts and the Planning and Compulsory Purchase Act 2004, with limited fiscal and legislative autonomy. Spain follows a decentralised administrative system where municipalities, including Barcelona, enjoy significant autonomy and can adapt policies to reflect local needs. For example, the Law on Local Regime Bases (Ley de Bases de Régimen Local) provides Barcelona with the authority to manage local services, regulate public spaces and implement urban policies. Thus the comparison between these local governments offers us ways to understand how leading city governments are tackling twin transition.

This paper is based on desk research and interviews carried out in Barcelona and Camden from April to September 2024. We conducted 20 semi-structured interviews (11 for Camden, nine for Barcelona), which were based on a joint research protocol developed in Lember et al 2025. Interviewees were city officials working on either the green or the digital transition, as well as in key sectors where transition twinning could take place, such as mobility, circularity and waste. We used the thematic analysis approach and the NVIVO software to analyse the results. We asked questions to understand the overall aims and framings of transition governance; the choices and design of transition pathways; and the approach to transition experiments. First, we have identified how each local administration conceptualised the directionality of the green, digital and twin transition. Second, we have abductively examined how the cities are building capabilities to drive the transitions in their respective directions.

Our methodological approach is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: Levels of analysis and research questions

Level (Lember et al, 2025)	Transition sphere (Loorbach, 2010)	Research questions
Transition governance (overall aims, values, framing)	Strategic (long-term cultural change)	1. How do cities conceptualise and participate in shaping the directionality of the green, digital and twin transitions? 2. How do cities develop capabilities for the green, digital and twin transitions?
Organisational strategies for transition pathways (choice and design of strategy and policy)	Tactical (dominant structures and institutions)	
Innovation portfolios as transition experiments (sources of novelty)	Operational (concrete innovation projects and actions)	

4. Case studies: The green, digital and twin transitions of Camden and Barcelona

Barcelona, the capital of Catalonia, is home to approximately 1.6 million residents (as of 2023). Barcelona is densely populated and serves as a significant cultural, economic and political hub in Spain. The city’s economy is diverse, driven by tourism, commerce, tech startups and a thriving manufacturing sector. In 2021, Barcelona’s GDP reached over €176 billion, contributing significantly to the Catalan and national economies. Barcelona has been led by progressive mayors in recent years, with Ada Colau, leader of the Barcelona en Comú (Barcelona in Common) party, serving as mayor from 2015-2023.

Camden, a central London borough, has a population of 210,400 (as of 2024) and covers nearly 22 square kilometres. The borough is known for its strong educational sector and as a hub for startups (The Camden Renewal Commission, 2020). Camden has seen remarkable economic growth, contributing £34.4 billion to the national economy in 2018, a 93% increase from 2008, outpacing growth rates in Central London, Greater London and the UK overall. Camden Council has been led by the Labour party for several years and by Georgia Gould from 2017-2024.

In what follows, for the cases of Camden and Barcelona we describe how the green, digital and combined twin transitions are being addressed by civil servants, first at the level of transition governance, followed by organisational strategies and finally at the level of innovation portfolios.

4.1 Barcelona

Transition governance

The city of Barcelona is a pioneer in digital government and has a comprehensive approach to the **digital transition**, which includes the transformation of public administration, digital innovation, digital inclusion, citizen participation, and the provision and protection of data commons. From 2011-2015, Barcelona first began prioritising digital transition and built partnerships with tech companies like IBM and Cisco, who ‘promoted the idea that a city could be run like an operating system, in much the same way as a computer itself’ (Monge et al, 2023).

The policy during this time sought to achieve greater efficiency, sustainability and opportunities for citizens and companies (Barcelona City Council, 2014). The intention was that the development of a smart city would open new business opportunities, and technology companies were offered the opportunity to test applications and technologies at no cost. In 2015, Ada Colau was elected as mayor, running for the Barcelona en Comú party, which emerged from social movements with no direct policy affiliation, and on a strong participatory democracy and people-centred agenda. For the digital transition, this meant switching from a smart city paradigm into a 'digital city' paradigm that was more related to people's needs and where data was governed by public interest (Charnock et al, 2021). Ada Colau and Barcelona en Comú retained the leadership in 2019, although in a different coalition, which continued with citizen-oriented policymaking, but also focused on 'building good relationships with large swathes of the private sector' (Interviewee 4). Nonetheless, interviewees repeatedly commented on the role of the city as serving its people through the digital transition: 'Simply put, the goal of our digital transition is people-oriented. It's to provide better services to our citizens. The private sector provides knowledge and software, but the orientation is people-centred. It goes beyond efficiency' (Interviewee 5).

Barcelona sees itself as an innovator in the digital realm and plays a role in designing and fostering technology and digital projects from scratch that are integrated across city departments and set precedents for other cities. Barcelona is considered a pioneer in the smart city movement internationally and gained a reputation for democratic approaches in the digital transition. It holds a leading role in networks such as the Cities Coalition for Digital Rights. One interviewee commented on the importance of balancing all these roles, not being captured by business interests or a discourse that is more pervasive for an international audience, and continuing to centre local support and needs.

The **green transition** is conceptualised as a fundamentally participatory and collaborative effort in Barcelona. The start of this current trajectory of climate and sustainability began in 2015 under Ada Colau's leadership. In 2015, Barcelona established a working group of 141+ organisations to sign up to the Citizen Commitment to Sustainability to define the Commitment to the Climate, a city roadmap on climate change. Today, this has evolved into Barcelona+Sostenible – a network of 800+ organisations signed up to the Commitment to the Climate, alongside the council. Interviewees mention that there are more resources in the private sphere that can support both transitions, which can also be win-win for both public and private. The struggle is to find the right interface and the right connections, and doing a lot of things for the first time, like deploying public-private systems of financing.

Barcelona does not have a governance approach to the **twin transition**. Both the green transition and digital transition are 'born from different places and quite distinct' (Interviewee 1). There are examples of projects and initiatives where the digital transition was at the service of the green transition, as well as examples of strategies or plans that integrate green and digital goals (for example the Green New Deal, Donut Economic Commitment or Digital Twin Project). Most interviewees had not heard of the twin transition before, but when the concept was explained, most spoke of examples of using digital tools to accelerate green goals, as opposed to reducing emissions from digital processes.

There is no existing strategy that explicitly links the green and digital transitions. One interviewee commented: 'This doesn't exist, because green transition is in one department and digital is in another one' (Interviewee 8). Several interviewees alluded to this gap and the need for a more explicit connection, in particular given the city's participation in the Net Zero Cities Mission, which strives for both smart and climate-neutral cities by 2030. Interviewees regularly commented on the role of the city as serving its people through both transitions, both by using participatory democratic approaches and by ensuring policy design does not have adverse effects on specific populations. Both transitions also hold elements of rights and justice (i.e. digital rights and climate justice) which shape both strategies. Across both transitions, interviewees consistently see the city's role as an activator, collaborator, enabler and network holder. The approach is one where the government activates and provides stewardship to different actors. It enables key players in market opportunities, and takes on innovative approaches via public-private partnerships and public procurement that involve private actors in the early definition of procurement itself.

Organisational strategies

In terms of the **digital transition**, the Barcelona Digital City Plan was first created in 2016 and then followed up with the Barcelona City Council Digital Transition Plan, which is the digital transformation roadmap for Barcelona. Its three main pillars are (1) digital transformation of the city council and the city; (2) digital innovation and development of the entrepreneurial and social innovation ecosystem; and (3) digital empowerment of citizens. The initial plan included a roadmap that established the values, goals and actions of the new digital vision for Barcelona, and, in Ethical Digital Standards, an open-source policy toolkit for cities to develop 'digital policies that put citizens at the center and make governments more open, transparent and collaborative' (Bria et al, 2024). It included guidelines and democratic digital standards, including a technological code of conduct; the migration to open-source software, open architectures and open standards; the adoption of agile methodologies to develop user-centric digital services; and the publication of a technology procurement handbook that specifies contractual clauses in procurement contracts, mandating transparency, open standards and open data (Monge et al, 2022). Critical to all this was a new data directive with data ethics, privacy and citizens' data sovereignty at its core (Monge et al, 2022). The 'data commons' became a key principle, which set out the belief that data should have collective value and benefits. The city made the Ethical Digital Standards Toolkit available on GitHub for others to use and distributed the toolkit via the Cities Coalition for Digital Rights.

Several organisational strategies are in place to address the **green transition**: In 2018, the city launched Barcelona's Climate Plan 2018 - 2030, an ambitious, Paris Agreement-compatible plan. It set out Barcelona's strategy to reduce emissions by 45% by 2030 en route to becoming carbon neutral by 2050 and was co-produced with citizens, centring climate justice and citizen action and 'putting the most vulnerable people at the centre of its policies' (C40 Knowledge Hub, 2018). On 15 January 2020 Barcelona declared a climate emergency and in 2021 updated its Climate Plan 2018-2030 with a renewed goal of achieving net zero by 2030. It also revamped the Barcelona Commitment to the Climate with Barcelona+Sostenible network, which it presented on 7 May 2024.

Today, Barcelona is part of the Net Zero Cities EU Mission project, which has committed to being net zero by 2030 within its Climate City Contract.

Several interviewees commented on how this plan was the most ambitious yet, taking an already ambitious plan and making it more so. Several interviewees also shared that a strong component of the plan is to ensure that vulnerable people's needs are met. Barcelona faces several barriers in the implementation of its green transition policy. For example, several interviewees pointed out that for more challenging policies – such as those that impact private car use – if the benefits are not tangible to most people, they will not be in support, which will mean that political leadership will be too timid to act.

Several interviewees pointed to this legitimacy, knowledge and messaging gap. Most interviewees commented that they did not think that the city would meet its carbon neutrality goal. Most interviewees said that it's an ambitious goal, but that the city does not have the resources and faces many barriers to be able to achieve it. Many seemed to imply that more radical shifts would be necessary to reach their targets. A few interviewees also commented on how addressing issues that have strong 'established interests' leads to heavy criticism, which leads to political leadership being 'more in favour of innovations that improve systems, and replace them very slowly and have agreement in them' (Interviewee 6).

While there is no explicit strategy for the **twin transition** in Barcelona, some strategies address the aims of both transitions. For example, the Barcelona Green Deal was created in 2021, a plan to lead Barcelona's transition towards a green, digital and more equitable economy, and an economic roadmap for the city for the period up to 2030. It also acted as a COVID-19 recovery plan, and it identifies priority sectors that couple the goals of achieving a more competitive, more sustainable and more equitable city model (Barcelona Green Deal, 2021). Between 2021 and 2023, a sum of 672 million euros were invested to carry out 66 specific actions based around ten main goals, which includes digital tools as a means to achieve green goals. A few interviewees pointed to the EU Mission for carbon neutral and smart cities being a starting point to formalise the twin transition goals in policy. Several interviewees commented on internal forums that ensure policies are aligned with major objectives (such as green and digital ones), and then lead to the creation of formal procedures and the adoption of these lenses for budgeting (e.g. climate budgeting): 'What we're hoping to do is use the Mission as an excuse to create spaces to speed up transition, create structures of governance where we can have all the actors on board' (Interviewee 3).

Innovation portfolios

New organisational structures and roles emerged in the context of the **digital transition** in Barcelona: the Municipal Data Office (OMD) was created in 2023, which is responsible for the management, quality, governance, analysis and dissemination of data from the Barcelona City Council, and its associated entities. The OMD also serves as the main system for organising and planning sociological research, and monitoring public opinion, statistical production and socioeconomic analysis of the city and environments of interest, which allows the publication of

high frequency data and the development of evidence-based public policies. Similarly, Francesca Bria was appointed as Chief Technology Information Officer in June of 2016. The position was created as an executive level role, representing the elevation of digital strategy from beyond that of IT.

Several successful innovation experiments were conducted in the context of the digital transition in Barcelona (a comprehensive list is available in Appendix 1). Prominently, Decidim is a digital platform for citizen participation that was launched in February 2016 to support the co-production of the Municipal Action Plan. The team for Decidim was in a citizen participation department whose activities were rooted in traditional community development and local planning (Smith and Martin, 2020). The platform initially featured 2000 proposals from the city council for citizens to comment on, and citizens and organisations were also able to make public proposals. The Decidim platform is now used by many other public administrations in Spain and another 19 countries, with up to 311 implemented instances (Tomas, 2023). The particularity of Decidim is its collaborative philosophy of free and open source software, creating a network of developers and users (Tomas, 2023). City OS is another innovation experiment on the back of the digital transition in Barcelona. The app integrates the open sensor platform Sentilo and the city's various analytics dashboards, creating a 'platform for managing and analysing city data with common ontologies' through a 'single window'. This uses data to provide better services and optimise internal processes. This infrastructure allows for better data governance, to have more effective quality, privacy and security controls, and, above all, to provide the city council with a global vision in this area. In addition, the city council is also equipped with a structure where city decisions are made based on informed decisions (data driven). City OS works both with internal city council data (awarding of contracts, subsidies, projects of the Municipal Action Plan, districts, etc.) and with that of external agencies, including information about services that the city is responsible for, but that the council does not manage directly (transport, energy, environment, etc.).

The **green transition** also saw several successful innovation experiments in Barcelona. Multiple interviewees commented on the importance of pedagogy and of senior leaders signalling the importance of climate change, because that makes everyone pay more attention to it and ultimately leads to action. The Climate Change and Sustainability Office is a strategic department, but doesn't 'sit on top'. It plays a strategic role and then implementation is passed on to other departments. One prominent innovation experiment that was implemented in the context of the green transition is the Superblock programme (a comprehensive list is available in Appendix 1). This programme aims to increase sustainable mobility, improve public spaces, improve neighbourhoods and reactivate the economy. The first pilot projects began in 2014 and increased pedestrian trips by 10% and cycling trips by 30% in its first two years. Since 2016, Barcelona has worked on implementing six fully functional superblocks in the city. Stakeholders involved in the 'open project', as they call it, varied from residents, city council, private companies, district organisations, non-governmental organisations, universities and expert institutions. Major pushback from the selected superblock neighbourhoods, especially the local shop owners, was experienced during the pilot run. The same may happen during the superblock rollout

in L'Eixample, because of the immensity of space in the discussion. The argument was that restricted car movement would affect business and their customer base will fall drastically. The city has also created several new internal processes and structures for collaboration, including: a core group in the Climate Change and Sustainability Office on the green transition that includes several departments across health, social rights, mobility, energy, the 2030 agenda, resilience and others; a group of all the municipal directors that began when the recent governments came into power; technical working groups made up of ten to 12 staff across relevant departments, which started in 2018.

In terms of innovation projects for the **twin transition**, several interviewees commented on how the pandemic led civil servants to start to 'see problems in a different way.' A working group of leaders across departments that was initiated during the pandemic has remained. Some examples of what this could look like include climate budgeting, which would need to include developing the capabilities for that (e.g. analysing investments in terms of how much the city is decarbonising – is it more effective to plant 10,000 trees or retrofit a building or build bike lanes, when resources don't allow for all the above). One of the tools that has influenced internal routines is the Open Data BCN – a platform with all the city's data, which is public and open access, and allows civil servants across departments to access data they need. One interviewee commented that many departments are interested in launching new approaches to innovation and working with departments that have a more explicit innovation mandate: 'There is a general sense that the old model is failing. These tensions (between the old and the new) exist' (Interviewee 2).

Several initiatives indicated innovation in organisational strategies and capabilities. A significant and unique example is the Urban Innovation Centre. This internal innovation agency has some autonomy from traditional departments and its central mission is to drive forward innovation within Barcelona City Council by bringing together different stakeholders, innovating bureaucratic structures and finding new ways to address challenges. It consistently collaborates with several different departments and also has its own unique governance with a board of 80+ external stakeholders. It has a unique methodology in that it uses different tools for different challenges: challenge system, regulatory sandbox, la ciudad proactiva, and other programmes, which all have some level of ecosystem management. One interviewee noted: 'There is a shift in trying to tackle problems in a more holistic way. Holistic approach means we need to change the way we organise. There is not one department that is driving this. Again, it depends on the unique situation that is faced in those departments.' (Interviewee 3). Several interviewees commented on how changing internal, institutional structures is critical for ensuring the consistency and longevity of transition goals, and momentum beyond political cycles.

4.2 Camden

Transition governance

Our interviews revealed a plurality of narratives around the **digital transition** in Camden, mainly related to striving for efficiency gains, digital inclusion and data rights. Multiple civil servants mentioned that the digital transition is about improving service delivery and the productivity of civil servants (Interviewee 4, Interviewee 6). Furthermore, as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, a strong emphasis on digital inclusion emerged in Camden (Interviewee 11). Several civil servants emphasised Camden's people-oriented approach to the digital transition, which aims to leave no staff or citizens behind (Interviewee 6, Interviewee 11), and strives to make public services citizen-focused, user-friendly and accessible (GDS Team, 2015). At the same time, the council focuses on digital rights and published a data charter in January 2022 that was developed through a deliberative process with citizens. The charter states that data should be used to improve residents' quality of life, while anticipating the unplanned outcomes from these uses of data. Digital rights are deemed important as an end in themselves, but also as an enabler, because, 'If we don't have a level of trust about people's information, and don't have a deeper legitimacy, then some of the tools of the digital age, we might not be able to use some of the tools that can drive efficiency and productivity in the public sector' (Interviewee 5). At the same time, one civil servant acknowledged that the digital transition also entails, 'the fundamental transition to a digital economy and society' (Interviewee 4), but this is not yet being addressed by the borough. In the digital transition, Camden been able to benefit from national policy and technical support by importing best practices in designing digital products and services from the Government Digital Service (GDS) and sharing its own learnings with other councils through the London Office of Technology and Innovation (LOTI) (Interviewee 4, Interviewee 3).

Camden Council's approach to the **green transition** is predominately participatory, bottom-up and focused on ensuring a just transition. The bottom-up momentum for climate action is exemplified by the fact that the council declared a climate emergency in 2019 after holding the UK's first citizen assembly on the climate crisis. Based on this citizen assembly, the Climate Action Plan was developed (Interviewee 1). Multiple interviewees emphasised the bottom-up nature of Camden's approach to the green transition, acknowledging that systems change towards decarbonisation requires the involvement of multiple actors, including local communities and businesses: 'The green transition [is] something that we're part of as an organisation, but we're not the whole' (Interviewee 1). This participatory culture seems to stem from the long-time Leader of the Council, Georgia Gould (Interviewee 2). In addition to this bottom-up approach, several interviewees acknowledged Camden's ability as a local council to take the lead by investing in its corporate estate and policy interventions in its built environment. One interviewee described it as: 'a mix between the bottom-up community-led interventions, and then also kind of leading by example, through our own corporate estate' (Interviewee 2). Camden is aware of the necessity of a socially just transition, which is supported by local communities: 'We're not an organisation where net zero is the only goal regardless of the social and financial costs for residents' (Interviewee 2). One view was that resilience is an increasingly important part of conceptualising the green transition: investing in adaptation and building resilience is 'a more

socially responsible use of the (limited) money' available (Interviewee 2). Multiple interviewees mentioned that a clear agenda and financial support from national government on the green transition would give Camden more legitimacy to take policy action. One civil servant explained: 'A lack of political vision holds us back at every level. I think we've got quite a clear political vision in Camden [but these visions are not the same at the city and at national level]. If you haven't got that sort of clarity of vision, from which funding priorities flow, that's a real uphill struggle' (Interviewee 1).

While there is a general sense that digital tools can support the green transition, there is no strategic conceptualisation of the **twin transition** in Camden. All interviewees working on the green transition in Camden mentioned that data is relevant for their work (i.e. that digital tools can be used for greener outcomes), but agreed that there is no strategic perspective on the relation between digitalisation and sustainability: 'Data is very much part of our work, but it's not like we're driving digital change. We're capitalising on digital change.' (Interviewee 2).

On the other hand, all interviewees working on the digital transition acknowledged that responding to climate change is important for the borough, although they do not focus on it in their work (Interviewee 6, Interviewee 11, Interviewee 3). At the same time, one interviewee mentioned the carbon emissions associated with digitalisation, asking, 'How do you minimise the reputational damage of doing more digital?' (Interviewee 6). While these questions are starting to be raised, they are not yet addressed at the strategic level by the borough, although several interviewees recognised that there is potential in exploring the topic further (Interviewee 10, Interviewee 3, Interviewee 4, Interviewee 5, Interviewee 2). While the twin transition is not addressed by any specific strategy, interviews showed that corporate strategy is perceived to have a role to play in the participatory relationship between council and communities when it comes to complex issues like green and digital transitions: 'I think the role of corporate strategy is to build connections and engage [with citizens through participatory for a], but then also to kind of challenge and mediate [with expert knowledge]' (Interviewee 5).

Since Camden does not have clear twin transition goals, it also does not engage in the long-term formulation of such goals in the context of national governance. The lack of a coherent political narrative at the national level related to the green and digital transition was mentioned as an obstacle for ambitious policy in Camden. As one civil servant explained: 'The kind of complexity of our government systems means that the preventative interventions needed around a just climate transition and a just digital transition [are incredibly challenging] in the absence of a coherent national strategy. [There is a] huge amount of political risk for local municipal authorities to take singular action where they expend a budget that is politically contested' (Interviewee 5).

Organisational strategies

In terms of strategies for the **digital transition**, the Camden Data Strategy (2023-2025) outlines how the council strives 'to be the pioneering leader in the use of data that measurably improves citizens' lives.' To achieve this bold vision, the strategy first aims to fix foundations, build data capability and excellence, and use innovations to empower frontline services. There is no broader

public digitalisation strategy in Camden, but the internal Digital and Data Service High Level Strategy outlines seven strategic themes, including building secure and stable infrastructure, and states that the borough will 'begin to transition to sustainable environments and processes in 2024.' A second strategic theme is about 'using data to drive positive change', which includes 'empower Camden's frontline delivery services with data'. However, in practice, the strategic twinning of the transitions is weak: 'There is a point [in the strategy] on running a sustainability project and looking at our impact on sustainability, but it's got no further than that, as far as I'm aware... To my knowledge, compared to everything else that's already on that plan, it's very much a bit of an afterthought at the moment' (Interviewee 6). This has been deliberate: 'We haven't focused on it as much as we necessarily should... because I've wanted us to focus on foundational stuff first' (Interviewee 3).

There are several strategies key for **green transition** in Camden. The Climate Action Plan (2020-2025) outlines an ambition for a zero-carbon Camden by 2030, based on a community vision around four pillars: people, buildings, places and organisations. The vision includes public awareness and participation through Camden's Citizen Panel, as well as participation of all businesses and organisations through the Camden Climate Change Alliance and the Camden Climate Pledge, which includes over 350 organisations collaborating to reduce their emissions. Furthermore, the Climate Adaptation and Resilience Plan (2023-2025) evaluates how climate hazards will affect Camden and devises a set of activities to improve the borough's resilience. The plan strives to provide the most support to those members of the community with greater vulnerability. In addition, the Camden Reduction and Recycling Plan (2023-2025) explains how Camden will work with our residents, communities and businesses to move towards a circular economy. Thus, these strategies all place an emphasis both on bottom-up participatory policy design as well as a collaborative implementation effort.

Camden has no explicit strategy on the **twin transition**, but some green transition strategies leverage digital tools. For example, the Climate Action Plan (2020-2025) mentions the creation of a public database of all renewable energy installations. Similarly, the Climate Adaptation and Resilience Plan (2023-2025) describes that data was key in the approach to understanding climate risk in Camden, such as health outcome data to integrate heat risk health advice into healthcare information, or flood risk data to support decision-making in emergencies. The We Make Camden (2023-2030) strategy was deemed by interviewees to be the closest thing to a twin transition strategy in Camden (Interviewee 4, Interviewee 5, Interviewee 3, Interviewee 6). Among the six challenges, two are explicitly linked to the twin transition: 'Digital: Everyone in Camden can access and be part of a digital society' and 'Climate emergency: Camden's local economy tackles the climate emergency.' Camden has more generally and consciously focused on upgrading its organisational capability in the context of adopting missions. Missions 'provided a sort of rationale to accelerate the investment in the organisational development required to experiment in the context of complexity' (Interviewee 4).

For example, Camden has invested significantly in human-centred design capabilities and developed in-house capacity to work with agile methods and design, and prototype and pilot initiatives within its corporate strategy department, and has upgraded its monitoring evaluation capacity by investing in a new insight, impact and learning team (Interviewee 4, Interviewee 5).

Innovation portfolios

The **digital transition** has focused on building foundational capability before becoming more tactical and strategic in directing innovations towards a specific aim. A general lack of digital capacity on behalf of the council was also mentioned as a barrier in Camden (Interviewee 2, Interviewee 3, Interviewee 1). As one civil servant explained: 'We first need to make sure that we have an infrastructure that is secure, stable, but also interoperable, and that will be able to change and evolve easier as the landscape evolves' (Interviewee 3). While capacity to drive the digital transition is still limited, the technology adoption team is starting to develop routines to prioritise the implementation of missions in Camden. To decide which projects and collaborations to pursue, the team developed a triaging form which prioritises those projects that relate to another challenge or mission across Camden: 'As a new team, we've built processes and ways to handle stuff coming in... I think, for a lot of local governments, whatever's breaking or on fire, that's what we have to help with first. I would say our data and digital services team has matured to start getting away from being so unplanned. I'm trying to push it to that next level, so that we can be more tactical' (Interviewee 6).

Almost all interviewees pointed to siloed organisational structures as another organisational barrier for implementing the **green transition**. There is a perception that the green transition is still driven mostly by the sustainability team (Interviewee 10) and that climate change is not felt as a priority across the organisation (Interviewee 6). Camden worked with Extinction Rebellion to introduce, in its constitution, a duty for all elected politicians to consider the environmental impacts of the decisions they take with a focus on climate change. According to one interviewee, this caused a 'mainstreaming of climate into the organisational governance, which really helped. So whilst it's still quite siloed, when someone gets to the point where they're going to bring their decision report through, they really have to work out what the environmental impact of this is' (Interviewee 2). Several projects opportunistically leverage the synergies between the two transitions in several policy areas (see Appendix 1 for full list). For example, by leveraging data and a collaboration with Google, Camden has launched publicly available clean air walking routes. Similarly, data helps to evaluate and adapt the effectiveness of sustainable transport schemes or flood risk mapping (Interviewee 2).

By introducing missions, Camden's organisational governance also became more conducive for addressing the **twin transition**: More specifically, the council created four new teams of policy designers, assembled from previously existing teams, to better enable experimentation, stakeholder engagement and risk-taking (Bellinson and Albala, 2021). The teams bring together policymakers with different specialisations, each under the direction of an elected councillor, to collaboratively encourage societal innovation in support of the mission. Interviews revealed that the structure of missions can be particularly helpful in the context of digitalisation: 'What you'll

normally get within digital transformation is incubating and testing a small piece of work, and then you build out certain things. In the public sector, this doesn't work, because it just delays the problems of cultural resistance to it' (Interviewee 3). However, some interviewees admitted that missions did not significantly increase the amount of collaboration between the green and digital transition: 'There's not a high amount of cross-challenges or cross-missions collaboration happening again. There's very few levers or drivers that are trying to encourage us to link any of the missions up with one another.' (Interviewee 6). Almost all interviewees mentioned a general lack of capacity and prioritisation of the twin transition as barriers to its implementation. While missions conceptually make sense, the roles that support their implementation are often allocated to civil servants who are already working beyond their capacity (Interviewee 3, Interviewee 6).

Interviewees also mentioned informal administrative routines that ensure collaboration between digital and green teams: 'On a holistic level, we're probably quite opportunistic, so where the digital... opportunity fits our green goals, we'd seek to leverage those' (Interviewee 1). This is expected to be done by the senior leadership team in Camden, who are responsible for bringing in colleagues with digital competencies when needed: 'If we're scoping a programme of work and there's a big digital component for that particular service area, you should know to bring them in' (Interviewee 1).

5. Discussion

Conceptualising directionality in the context of the digital, green and twin transitions

In Barcelona and Camden, the digital transition can be loosely conceptualised as 'steering selected particular pathways rather than others,' which Stirling (2024, p.14) calls the direction of innovation. In both cases, digital transformation is not simply about accelerating progress along the predominant direction for innovation, but about consciously choosing one possible direction over others (Ciarli, 2023). The case of Barcelona highlights how the digital transition is shaped by political values: Mayor Ada Colau championed the idea that data should serve the public interest, which led to the replacement of the smart city paradigm with the digital city paradigm (Charnock et al, 2021). Interviews corroborate that the goal of the digital transition in Barcelona is people-oriented: 'The private sector provides knowledge and software, but the orientation is to provide better services to our citizens' (Interviewee 4). In the digital transition, where the most powerful driving force of innovation is often the private sector driven by economic efficiency goals (Muench et al, 2022), this marks a clear deviation of the direction away from the 'most powerfully-favored forms of innovation' (Stirling, 2024, p.7) towards one that brings value to citizens. Similarly, Camden views digitalisation as a tool to make public services citizen-focused, user-friendly and accessible (GDS Team, 2015). Its strong emphasis on digital inclusion as an urgent challenge to be addressed post-COVID showcases that digital innovation can be intentionally directed. As one interviewee explained in the context of procurement: 'The thing that's holding back [the] local authority and public sector in general is not the people in the institution. It's the ecosystem of suppliers that they've got' (Interviewee 3).

Instead of being constrained by the quality offered by the private sector, Camden Council is striving to reshape the landscape to access innovations aligned with its strategic priorities.

Turning to the green transition, both Barcelona and Camden's approach appears to resemble an effort to navigate the pluralities of multiple possible ends, which Stirling (2024) describes as shaping the directionality of innovation. In Barcelona, the green transition appears to be more politically contested than the digital one, requiring the public sector to balance 'multiple social agencies concurrently across diverse alternative orientations' (Stirling, 2024). This is illustrated by the high contestation around the Superblock programme pilot project, especially from local shop owners, which invited the participation of a wide range of stakeholders in an openly collective response to the green transition. Similarly, Camden's Climate Action plan was developed based on the 2019 citizen assembly and continues to be guided by a Citizen Panel (Interviewee 1). The citizen-centred approach is, 'very disruptive, because it leads to quite unexpected policy outcomes. I think if we, as experts, had written a climate plan for Camden, we would have ended up focusing a lot more on the technical stuff... Instead, we've got this kind of grassroots community vision for what people really want to see' (Interviewee 2). This illustrates how Camden did not just direct the green transition towards the direction its civil servants deemed relevant, but opened up the process to citizens themselves and thus to the many different futures that Camden's residents may deem desirable.

When it comes to the combined twin transition, the need for public sector organisations to drive the directionality of innovation (Stirling, 2024) becomes even more apparent in both the cases of Barcelona and Camden. The twin transition requires civil servants to hold simultaneously not only the plurality of possible directionalities in the green and digital transitions respectively, but to consider them at their intersection. The fact that neither Camden nor Barcelona, nor any of the cities studied by Lember and others (2025), exhibit explicit twin transition strategies illustrates just how challenging this is to implement. In the face of this challenge, it appears tempting for civil servants to ask for guidance from higher levels of governance: In the case of Camden, the lack of a national twin transition strategy was mentioned as a barrier for the local twin transition, and in Barcelona several interviewees mentioned that the EU Mission for climate neutral and smart cities could provide a helpful narrative for twinning the two transitions. However, embracing the directionality of the twin transition would require a more multilevel and multistakeholder approach, rooted in the local governments and citizens themselves. One civil servant in Camden explained that corporate strategy could play a role in shaping the relationship between the council and local communities when it comes to complex issues like green and digital transitions: 'I think the role of corporate strategy is to build connections and engage with citizens [through participatory fora], but also to challenge and mediate [with expert knowledge]' (Interviewee 5). Through such approaches, local governments are starting to address the directionality questions posed by the twin transition.

In sum, our empirical analysis shows that different conceptualisations of directionality, according to Stirling (2025), apply to the digital, green and twin transitions in the cases of Barcelona and Camden. While the digital transition seems to resemble the direction of innovation, the green and twin transitions have a plurality of possible ends that are each favoured by different stakeholders

and thus need to be mediated and balanced by public sector organisations. Thus, it is pertinent to explore whether distinct capabilities are required to drive the transition governance, organisational strategies and innovation portfolios of the respective transitions.

Identifying public sector capabilities required for the digital, green and twin transitions

Capabilities for the digital transition

The case of Barcelona revealed several capabilities required for the digital transition, mainly centred around giving direction and supporting the new, as well as reflexivity, learning and experimenting. At the level of transition governance, the city seems to be focussing on its capability for reflexivity, learning and experimenting (Janssen et al, 2023). The city develops and tests projects which it then integrates across city departments, setting precedents for other cities to follow (Interviewee 3). While the direction of innovation is determined by politics (such as through Ada Colau prioritising citizen-orientation), many policy experiments, such as Decidim, were tested and spread without contestation. At the level of organisational strategies, Barcelona seems to be mainly utilising capabilities to support the new (Braams et al, 2022): the Digital Transition Plan made it a priority to develop a strong entrepreneurial and social innovation ecosystem in Barcelona, from which new innovation solutions could emerge. Furthermore, initiatives such as the Ethical Digital Standards Toolkit exemplify Barcelona's capability to set a normative direction, which is spread across government departments and society (Braams et al, 2022). Notably, Barcelona has also created new institutions, which allow it to maintain these capabilities, such as the Municipal Data Office and elevating the role of Chief Technology Information Officer to executive level, which contributed to making Barcelona a pioneer in digital government.

Like Barcelona, Camden seems to be focussing on the capability to reflect, learn and experiment, especially from best practice examples from the national Government Digital Service (GDS) and through exchange with other municipalities through the London Office of Technology and Innovation (LOTI). Comparable to Barcelona, Camden seems to make use of its capability to set a clear direction with its data strategy, to ensure that the use of data improves citizens' lives (Braams et al, 2022). Interviews revealed that Camden is using its capability to chart an acceptable development pathway (Schot and Steinmüller, 2018) and, recognising the importance of maintaining their trust, citizens' data is used to avoid contestation in future digitisation projects. Camden is building internal dynamic capabilities to seize new innovative solutions from the private sector (Kattel, 2022), for example by changing the senior leadership team from general managers into subject matter experts (Interviewee 3).

Capabilities for the green transition

When it comes to the green transition, Barcelona relies on its capability to coordinate collective movements by creating supportive governance structures (Braams et al, 2022) and destabilise unsustainable systems. Barcelona has created governance structures that enable a collective movement both within the government and with its external stakeholders (Janssen et al, 2023). The most significant example is Barcelona's Urban Innovation Centre, which enables innovation

both across departmental silos and by attracting novel solutions from external stakeholders through co-financing, testing and scaling them for public procurement. In addition, to coordinate within government, several interviewees cited the importance of climate leaders within the city administration, and the important strategic and coordinating role played by the Climate Change and Sustainability Office. Interviewees also emphasised cities' coordinating role through Barcelona+Sostenible, which convenes a network of 800+ organisations that have made a commitment to address climate change. Beyond its capability to create supportive governance structures, the green transition requires Barcelona to destabilise the unsustainable (Braams et al, 2022). Destabilising the unsustainable is key for the green transition, but challenging due to the high level of political contestation of policies that require behavioural change, such as those that impact private car use (Interviewee 3). The interviews showed that this results in the prioritisation of innovations that incrementally improve systems, rather than fundamentally transform them (Interviewee 6).

Similarly, Camden relies on its capability to support governance, coordinate collective movements and destabilise unsustainable systems through participatory platforms, as well as having the capability to resolve conflicts where ideas for the desirable direction of innovation diverge. Participatory platforms and bottom-up demand for climate action through the citizen assembly served as a driver that helped to legitimise and catalyse climate action on behalf of Camden Council (Interview Harald Garner) (Janssen et al, 2023). The borough used its capabilities to create governance structures that 'make space for a great variety of voices, arguments and interpretations in the design process of transition policy' (Braams et al, 2022) by creating a citizen panel to accompany the implementation of the Climate Action Plan and by developing the missions within We Make Camden, together with community representatives in the Renewal Commission. By involving citizens in the policy design process, Camden embraces the contestation, complexity and uncertainty (Schot and Steinmueller, 2018) that is inherent in transition policymaking, and uses its capability to resolve conflicting ideas for the desirable direction for change before policies are implemented (Janssen et al, 2023). In terms of strategies for the green transition, civil servants in Camden also rely on the capability to destabilise the unsustainable. This capability was strengthened through a constitutional change which made climate considerations mandatory in decision-making and is used, for example, in the transport sector, where investment in segregated cycling infrastructure can be said to be destabilising the transport system by taking out road space for cars (Interviewee 7).

Capabilities for the twin transition

Since neither Barcelona nor Camden have explicit twin transition strategies, we explore how the lack of such capabilities is preventing the city administrations from connecting the two transitions. In the case of Barcelona, while there are examples of initiatives where digital tools were used to address green transition aims, such as the Digital Twin Project, this was more at the instrumental rather than the institutional level (Meijer, 2024). One possible explanation is that Barcelona lacks the sense-making (or system awareness) capabilities (Kattel, 2022) that would allow it to think of the green and digital transitions jointly at a systems level (Weber and Rohracher, 2012), and across trans- and multidisciplinary epistemological boundaries (Janssen

et al, 2023). This is challenging to do because of the high demand for coordination capabilities in the context of the twin transition: It requires public organisations to consider all the actors involved across both transitions, and incorporate their many different perceptions of the problem and their views on what approaches could best address them. Furthermore, embracing legitimacy and strategic leadership capabilities for the twin transition on behalf of the city administration (Janssen et al, 2023) would allow Barcelona to leverage institutional structures such as the Urban Innovation Centre even more effectively, and convene different stakeholders and city departments to innovate specifically for the twin transition.

In Camden, there is a notable absence of a coherent twin transition vision at the institutional level. While the We Make Camden strategy addresses both transitions through its missions and challenges, this has not translated into strategic collaboration on the twin transition. Ironically, the governance structure, designed to break down silos, has instead created mission and challenge teams that, while each internally cross-departmental and collaborative in design, remain isolated from one another. As with Barcelona, this may stem from a lack of sense-making or system awareness capabilities (Kattel, 2022). However, Camden also faces a more fundamental challenge: a lack of general capacity. Many interviewees noted that while the missions are conceptually sound, the roles required for their implementation are often assigned to civil servants already stretched beyond their limits. This capacity gap makes prioritising the twin transition highly unlikely. As one interviewee explained: 'With something like the twin transition, it would have to be me and someone from environmental services jointly leading an initiative that would look at those things together, and the chances of that happening end up being quite slim, if I'm being honest with you' (Interviewee 3). In a political climate where local government budgets have been significantly reduced, Camden must adopt nimble and resource-efficient approaches to the twin transition. Promisingly, the council is building its capacity for reflexivity, learning and experimentation (Janssen et al, 2023) by establishing an insight, impact and learning team, and enhancing its in-house capabilities for agile methods and design (Interviewee 5). These developments suggest that while capacity constraints present challenges, Camden is taking steps towards creating the foundational capabilities conducive to addressing the twin transition.

In sum, in line with our propositions, different capabilities seem prevalent for addressing the digital, green and twin transitions respectively. For the digital transition, both Barcelona and Camden relied on giving direction for innovation in a top-down manner, as well as learning, experimenting and seizing new innovations that align with its policy direction. While Barcelona has established institutions and structures to maintain these capabilities and perceives itself to be a pioneer in digital government, Camden has more recently hired civil servants with such capabilities and is focusing on 'fixing the foundations.' In the context of the green transition, both cities seem to additionally rely on their capability to support governance through participatory platforms and collective movements, destabilising unsustainable systems and resolving conflicts where ideas for the desirable direction of innovation diverge. Finally, the twin transition seems to demand even more complex capabilities on behalf of Barcelona and Camden, such as systems-level sensemaking capabilities and the ability to engage stakeholders across both transitions and trans- and multidisciplinary epistemological boundaries.

6. Conclusions

This paper has explored how the twin transition is conceptualised and governed in the context of two European cities. We have shown that the cases of Barcelona and Camden are examples of how cities can develop capabilities for the twin transition, but that there are also significant challenges involved in doing so. Our findings suggest that the different directionalities underlying the green and digital transitions require different capabilities for their implementation. This is because the green transition is driven by normative, political goals, while the digital transition is driven by economic and efficiency goals. As a result, cities need to develop separate strategies, tactics and capabilities to advance the twin transition.

Our findings also suggest that the twin transition requires a unique set of capabilities that is not simply the sum of the capabilities required for the green and digital transitions. This is because the twin transition requires cities to integrate the green and digital transitions in a way that is both effective and equitable. The challenge for cities is to develop the capabilities necessary to overcome these challenges and implement the twin transition in a way that is both effective and equitable. This will require cities to develop a clear understanding of the different directionalities underlying the green and digital transitions. It will also require cities to develop a unique set of capabilities that is tailored to the specific challenges of the twin transition.

We believe that our findings have significant implications for policy and practice. We believe that our findings can help cities to develop more effective strategies for implementing the twin transition, but the cities might need stronger national level support to do so. We also believe that our findings can help ensure that the twin transition is implemented in a way that is both effective and equitable.

Future research should focus on the following areas:

- The development of a more nuanced understanding of the different directionalities underlying the green and digital transitions.
- The identification of the specific capabilities that are required for the twin transition.
- The development of case studies of cities that are successfully implementing the twin transition.

We believe that future research in these areas can help to ensure that the twin transition is implemented in a way that is both effective and equitable.

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Appendix: Innovation portfolios (twin transition)

Barcelona: twin transition projects

- **Decidim:** A digital platform for citizen participation that was funded by the D-Cent initiative (Decentralised Citizens Engagement Technologies was a Europe-wide project supporting open source, distributed and privacy-aware tools for direct democracy and economic empowerment), this was developed specifically for Barcelona and launched in February 2016 to support the co-production of the Municipal Action Plan. The Decidim team was in a citizen participation department whose activities were rooted in traditional community development and local planning (Smith and Martin, 2020). The platform initially featured 2000 proposals from the city council for citizens to comment on, and citizens and organisations were also able to make public proposals. The Decidim platform is now used by many other public administrations in Spain and another 19 countries, with up to 311 implemented instances (Tomas, 2023). The particularity of Decidim is its collaborative philosophy of free and open source software, creating a network of developers and users (Tomas, 2023).
- **Connectem:** A digital-needs support service, this aims to ensure access to digital devices with high-quality internet connections and digital support for people at risk of digital exclusion. It is a tool for combating the digital gap and addressing the emergency situation caused by the rapid digitalisation of basic activities, such as education, job-hunting and administrative procedures, as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. Projects include services such as loaning laptop computers to low-income households. The project is the result of collaboration between the Barcelona Libraries Consortium, the BIT Habitat Foundation and the Barcelona Mobile World Capital Foundation.
- **Sentilo:** An open platform for managing sensors and actuators, this allows open access to data and increased interoperability, and is 'open to experimentation'. It is built, used and supported by an active and diverse community of cities and companies, who believe that using open standards and free software is the first 'smart' decision a smart city should take. This network of sensors captures flow of people and bicycles along the city's roads, decibel levels, temperature and quality of air, among other things.
- **City OS:** By integrating the open sensor platform Sentilo and the city's various analytics dashboards, this creates a platform for managing and analysing city data with common ontologies through a single window. This uses data to provide better services and optimise internal processes. The infrastructure allows for better data governance, better quality privacy and security controls, and, above all, provides the city council with a better overview. The city council is also equipped with a structure where city decisions are made based on informed (data-driven) decisions. City OS works both with internal city council data (awarding contracts, subsidies, Municipal Action Plan projects, districts, etc.) and the data of external agencies, including information about services that the city is responsible for, but that the council does not manage directly (transport, energy, environment, etc.).

- **Decode:** The aim of Decode (Decentralised Citizen Owned Data Ecosystem) is to develop decentralised technologies (such as blockchain) to give people greater control over their data. It is part of a European-wide project. The primary pilot project, Digital Democracy and Data Commons, gives city residents the opportunity to be active in choosing how their data is used. They contribute to a 'common data infrastructure', which is then open to use by local businesses, cooperatives and social organisations so that they can provide data-focused services and create long-term value for the public.
- **Digital Twin:** This project is the first phase of a collaboration with the Barcelona Supercomputing Center, the Centro Nacional de Supercomputación (BSC-CNS), which, together with the support of the Municipal Institute of Informatics (IMI) and Barcelona Regional (BR), has created simulations and predictions about the impact of certain projects or public policies. The Digital Twin is a digital copy of the city of Barcelona, representing a highly detailed but static photograph, with the ultimate aim of creating a city-wide modelling programme (Euro Cities, 2023). The model aims to reproduce how different physical, social and digital systems impact each other and the city. One of the aims is to use the data to decarbonise and ensure that the right data is being collected. In the interviews, some civil servants commented that they were unsure about its utility and whether it will be able to answer some of their most useful questions.
- **The Urban Data Desk:** An urban and territorial data viewer, measuring 6 × 4 meters and controlled by four touch monitors, this offers an interactive experience with multiple layers of geo-referenced information (mobility, housing, public space, green infrastructure, flows, equipment, etc.) updated in real time.
- **SciTech DiploHub:** The Barcelona Science and Technology Diplomacy Hub is a non-profit public-private partnership that includes research centres, universities, non-profits, start-ups, corporations and public institutions, with the mandate to elevate the role of science, technology and cities in foreign policy, and make Barcelona a more influential player on the global stage through its contribution to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It has set out on five missions, all connected to Barcelona's role as an innovation capital and promoting multi-stakeholder dialogue (OECD OPSI, 2023).
- **Superblock programme:** This programme aims to increase sustainable mobility, improve public space, improve neighbourhoods and sites, and reactivate the economy. The first pilot projects began in 2014 and pedestrian trips increased by 10% and cycling trips by 30% in its first two years. Since 2016, Barcelona has worked on implementing six fully functional superblocks in the city. Stakeholders involved in the 'open project', as they call it, have varied from residents, city council, private companies, district organisations, non-governmental organisations, universities and expert institutions. Major pushback from the selected superblock neighbourhoods, especially the local shop owners, was experienced during the pilot run. The same may happen during the superblock rollout in L'Eixample, because of the immensity of space in the discussion. The argument was that restricted car movement would affect business and their customer base would fall drastically.

Camden: twin transition projects

- **Universal basic services (UBS) agenda:** In collaboration with the UCL Institute for Global Prosperity, Camden is experimenting with a universal basic services agenda, which delivers universal provision of key public services, including access to digital tools, to enable economic and civic participation for all citizens (Camden Inclusive Economy, 2021). One of the clear rationales for UBS is around the climate transition (Interviewee 4). Two interviewees agreed that this is one starting point for bringing the green and digital transition into a more coherent alignment (Interviewee 4 and Interviewee 5).
- **STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics) Commission:** As part of Camden's future skills agenda, this programme equips Camden's young people with skills and opportunities in the digital, scientific and creative industries (Interviewee 8, Interviewee 9). One interviewee explained that it, 'brings together, I guess for me in a positive sense, that we as an organisation believe that... local economic growth in Camden will come from work [the] within green and sustainable sectors and also work in our growing digital economy' (Interviewee 5).
- **Device Recycling Project:** Rather than selling old laptops to a recycling supplier, Camden is rethinking how old devices from its employees could benefit the local community, and thereby simultaneously promote digital inclusion and greener outcomes (Interviewee 11).
- **Clean air walking routes:** Through leveraging data and a collaboration with Google, Camden has launched publicly available clean air walking routes (Interviewee 2).
- **Flood risk mapping:** Camden is exploring a possible collaboration with Google to integrate topography and drainage capacity into Google's live weather app, to derive seven-day views on flood risk. However, the project is in its nascent stages: 'So you know, that I can see how... it's heading in that direction, but we're currently not really using that kind of stuff in Camden' (Interviewee 2).
- **Somers Town Carbon Credit Scheme:** Enabled by a complex digital solution which verifies the carbon credits, organisations can offset their emissions by purchasing carbon credits prevent carbon dioxide emissions by investing in retrofit (Interviewee 1).
- **Scone App:** In the Somers Town Future Neighbourhood community, Camden is trialling an app which allows users to track and understand how their actions impact the environment, and receive regular tips and ideas to take action (Somers Town Future Neighbourhood, n.d.). Early results are mixed: 'It's not really being picked up... It's like Twitter or something like that – you end up with a few people are always posting and it doesn't really quite connect with everyone' (Interviewee 2).

- **Digital Tenant Participation Project:** Rather than using paper surveys or inefficient and fragmented data collection systems, Camden designed an app that led into one database when conducting lots of data from an on-premise storage into the cloud: 'One of the messages from that is, don't take all the data with you, to save costs and reduce CO2 emissions' (Interviewee 6). While emission reductions are not the main motivation for the project, it is a benefit (Interviewee 6).
- **Updating procurement practices for technology and data:** Camden is including sustainability considerations in its procurement practices: 'We've just redone all of our procurement practices within technology and data, and we're starting to make sure that there's a lot more focus around sustainability and environmental considerations moving forward within our kind of selection criteria' (Interviewee 3).

